

Development of a general purpose cognitive-behavioral symptom taxonomy

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ABSTRACT

Motivation: Cognitive-behavior symptoms (CBSx) represent the surface manifestation of diverse etiology. Identification and documentation of CBSx are critical to biomedical research that targets understanding the association between the symptoms and the underlying causes including genetics, aging, injury, substance use, or infection. Seeing the lack of a semantic resource of CBSx, specifically dedicated to the symptom layer, we sought to develop a CBSx Taxonomy.

Methods: We defined CBSx as any observable abnormality or reduced capacity in certain cognitive or behavioral functionality. We also collected concepts concerning the impact of CBSx on life quality and daily activities. The taxonomy was iteratively developed by synthesizing knowledge from the literature, existing biomedical ontologies, and clinical instruments that assess CBSx in patients. The concepts were manually mapped to the Unified Medical Language System (UMLS). A domain expert in aging and neurodegenerative diseases was consulted in curating the CBSx Taxonomy.

Results: The derived taxonomy contains 258 concepts that are grouped into four major branches: cognitive symptoms, psychomotor symptoms, behavioral symptoms, and impact on life. The taxonomy has been implemented into a computable format and made available to the research community.

Conclusion: By synthesizing multiple knowledge sources, we developed the CBSx Taxonomy to serve as a dedicated semantic layer for cognitive-behavioral symptoms. The taxonomy is shared publicly and is expected to benefit diverse applications including natural language processing, phenotyping, and semantic harmonization.

1 INTRODUCTION

Interest in studying the dysfunction of brain and the detection of its symptomatic precursors has been of top priority in both clinical practice and research for centuries. When the brain is compromised, even modestly, it often manifests as an observable change that deviates from normal cognition or behavior – referred to as cognitive-behavioral symptoms (CBSx). The cognitive component aligns with task-completing functionality, while the behavioral component aligns with the psychosocial traits exhibited by a person. A compelling rationale to consider behavior jointly with cognition is the evidence that indicates association between the two aspects, including differential prognosis (Ismail et al., 2016). In addition to CBSx, consequential life impediments reported by an individual can provide nuanced information for diagnostic screening or outcome tracking.

As CBSx could be the initial signs of possible underlying dysfunction, identifying and measuring CBSx are critical steps in biomedical research of the brain. Therefore, a unified resource for the semantic representation of CBSx will be extremely useful. There have been activities in creating CBSx-related conceptual models including ontologies to help organize the accumulated knowledge. However, the existing work has focused largely on individual brain diseases, e.g., (Malhotra et al., 2014), and limited work has focused on CBSx. A symptom-centered layer also offers the potential for versatile use cases that are not bound to any specific etiology. For example, dedicated semantic tooling for CBSx will greatly assist in capturing subtle traces of brain dysfunction (transient or persistent) due to a wide array of causes including genetics, aging, injury, substance use, or infection (e.g., COVID neurocognitive complication). Furthermore, a CBSx semantic backbone can be naturally furnished with lexical variants to serve applications such as natural language processing.

To build a comprehensive semantic-lexical resource for CBSx, we first created a semantic taxonomy with hierarchically organized concepts. We synthesized content from the literature, existing ontologies, and clinical instruments that assess various subsets of CBSx. The CBSx Taxonomy is publicly available and contains 258 concepts organized into four major branches.

2 METHODS

By reviewing the literature on CBSx, we first determined the scope of the concepts and formed a taxonomy framework accordingly. The taxonomy was then iteratively refined both in terms of structure and contents by synthesizing general biomedical ontologies, topic-specific ontologies, and clinical instruments that

assess CBSx in patients. Lastly, the CBSx Taxonomy was audited by consulting a domain expert and implemented into a computable format.

2.1 Defining the scope of the CBSx Taxonomy

Regardless of the underlying etiology, we initially defined CBSx as any observable abnormality or reduced capacity in certain cognitive or behavioral functionality. In addition to the direct observables, we also collected various concepts regarding the impact of CBSx on life quality manifested as compromised daily activities.

2.2 Development of the CBSx Taxonomy

A set of seed articles (Apostolova & Cummings, 2008; Dillon et al., 2013; Finkel, Costa e Silva, Cohen, Miller, & Sartorius, 1996; Gallagher, Fischer, & Iaboni, 2017; Ismail et al., 2017; Ismail et al., 2016; McCarten, 2013; McWhirter, Ritchie, Stone, & Carson, 2020; Teri, Borson, Kiyak, & Yamagishi, 1989) on diseases that exhibit CBSx were identified by searching PubMed and Google Scholar. Two of the authors (JWF and LW) derived an initial taxonomy with concepts that were loosely categorized as cognitive or behavioral symptoms.

On top of the base taxonomy, we started from four general biomedical ontologies (upper half of **Table 1**) that are known to contain CBSx concepts and might inform organizing of the concepts. For example, we reviewed concepts under the MeSH subtree led by D019954: Neurobehavioral Manifestations, which has one of its entry terms being exactly “Cognitive Symptoms”. Two authors (JWF and LW) reviewed and incrementally merged the content and structure of each ontology one at a time. When disagreement occurred, they met to discuss and obtain consensus. After that, several topic-specific ontologies (lower half of **Table 1**) were reviewed and incorporated. In the process we also surveyed additional sources such as the Neurological Disease Ontology (Jensen et al., 2013) but gained minimal additions to the symptoms.

Upon incorporating the ontologies, the concept coverage and taxonomy structure stabilized. As a further enrichment, we reviewed and integrated clinical instruments that involve assessment of CBSx or impact on routine life activities. For example, the Clinical Dementia Rating includes the question “Rate the patient’s ability to cope with small sums of money (e.g., work out change, leave a tip)”, which assesses an instrumental function in daily life. The specific instruments that contributed to additional concepts are listed in **Table 2**. An author (LW) with informatics and medical knowledge assigned UMLS identifiers to the concepts in the CBSx Taxonomy. A program was created to automatically populate the UMLS core synonyms and cross references to the HPO, ICF, MeSH, and SNOMED-CT. The final taxonomy was audited by consulting a physician scientist (RCP) specialized in aging and neurodegenerative diseases.

Table 1. Ontologies with contents incorporated into the CBSx Taxonomy

Ontology name	Contributing area(s)
Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO) (Robinson et al., 2008)	Cognitive, Psychomotor
SNOMED CT – U.S. version	Cognitive, Behavioral
Medical Subject Headings (MeSH)	Cognitive, Psychomotor
International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF) (Cieza & Stucki, 2008)	Impact on life
Activities of Daily Living Ontology (Woznowski, Tonkin, & Flach, 2018)	Impact on life
Alzheimer Disease Ontology (Malhotra et al., 2014)	Cognitive
Multilingual Alzheimer Disease Ontology: ontoAD (Drame et al., 2014)	Cognitive, Behavioral

Table 2. Clinical instruments with contents incorporated into the CBSx Taxonomy

Instrument name	Contributing area(s)
Clinical Dementia Rating	Cognitive, Impact on life
Functional Activities Questionnaire	Impact on life
Short Test of Mental Status	Cognitive

3 RESULTS

The derived taxonomy (as of April 12, 2022) contains 258 concepts that are grouped under four major branches: cognitive symptoms, psychomotor symptoms, behavioral symptoms, and impact on life. The cognitive symptoms represent malfunction in the brain’s ability to process input or output information, while the behavioral symptoms relate more to the soft aspects including abnormal character or emotion. The psychomotor symptoms were separated into their own branch as suggested by our domain expert, for they present the brain’s impaired ability in controlling body movements. Each concept has been provided with core synonyms and cross references to HPO, ICF, MeSH, SNOMED-CT or UMLS if available. We summarize the top two levels of the current taxonomy and provide example descendent concepts in **Table 3**. The CBSx Taxonomy has been implemented in the OWL format (see **Fig.1** for a snapshot in Protégé) and is made available at <https://github.com/OHNLPCogBehavInfo>.

Table 3. Structure and content summary of the CBSx Taxonomy

1 st level	2 nd level	Example concepts in the subsumed levels
Cognitive symptoms	Reduced consciousness or focus	Inattention, lethargy, decreased vigilance, brain fog
	Memory issue	Declarative memory loss, Procedural memory loss
	Perceptual disturbance	Agnosia, anosmia, hallucination
	Language issue	Aphasia, agraphia
Psychomotor symptoms	Impaired thinking or reasoning	Disorientation, bradyphrenia
	Apraxia	Gait disturbance, ideomotor apraxia
Behavioral symptoms	Ataxia	General motor restlessness, tremors
	Personality change	Aggression, apathy
	Mental stress or distortion	Depressed, anxiety, compulsive behavior
Impact on life	Disrupted biological routine	Insomnia, loss of appetite
	Basic activities	Difficulty dressing oneself, difficulty with showing or bathing
	Instrumental activities	Difficulty with shopping, difficulty with making appointments

Fig. 1. Screenshot of the CBSx Taxonomy implemented in a computable format, showing information of the concept Apathy in the right panel.

4 CONCLUSIONS

We developed the CBSx Taxonomy to serve as a dedicated semantic layer for cognitive-behavioral symptoms. Based on synthesizing contents from the literature, existing ontologies, and clinical instruments, the resulting taxonomy currently contains 258 concepts that are organized into four major branches. The ongoing work is to continue curating the concepts, to furnish an accompanying lexicon and to formally evaluate the resource in the context of real use cases.

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